

SHORT ALUMINOSILICATE FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

Oxide ceramic fibers were developed many years ago and have found extensive use as high temperature insulation and refractory. Recently, oxide ceramic fibers have been used in reinforcing metals and polymers. These ceramic fibers offer reasonable high temperature properties at low cost.

Characteristics of Standard Oil's aluminosilicate type fibers and their application as a reinforcement for aluminum alloys are described. The improvement in tensile and fatigue properties, especially at elevated temperature, of aluminum alloys by incorporation of aluminosilicate fibers is demonstrated.

INTRODUCTION

Metal Matrix Composites, until recently, have been utilized almost exclusively in aerospace and military applications. The first high volume commercial application was introduced for diesel engine pistons in the early 1980's in Japan. The ceramic fiber was used to improve the wear resistance of the ring groove in an aluminum alloy piston (1). At present, reinforcing the piston crown with short ceramic fiber, as shown in Figure 1, is being viewed by many piston manufacturers in the United States and Europe as the most effective and attractive approach to improve the performance of heavy duty engines.

Figure 1 — Fiber Preforms and Reinforced Pistons

Donomoto et. al. (1) incorporated .05 to .07 volume fraction alumina and aluminosilicate fibers in AA336.0 aluminum alloy by squeeze casting. They observed a 60% and 90% reduction in wear depth over the base alloy when aluminosilicate and alumina fibers, respectively, were introduced in the base alloy. An increase in seizure resistance by 50%, a 10 to 20% decrease in the coefficient of thermal expansion, and a decrease in thermal fatigue deformation were also reported.

Toaz and Smalc (2, 3) have squeeze cast AA332.0 aluminum alloy with 5 vol. % aluminosilicate fiber, as well as 5 vol. % and 15 vol. % alumina fiber. An increase in ultimate tensile strength, yield strength, elastic modulus, hardness, wear resistance and a decrease in thermal expansion with respect to the base alloy were observed.

Spengler and Young (4) have also observed the improvement in hardness, ultimate tensile strength and fatigue strength over the base aluminum alloy AA339.0 when 10 or 20 vol. % alumina fiber was incorporated into the alloy by squeeze casting. The improvement is more pronounced at higher temperature.

Clyne et. al. (5) published a comprehensive paper concerning the fabrication of alumina fiber reinforced aluminum alloys utilizing the squeeze casting method. The pressure and infiltration rate characteristics of the fabrication process were explored. Only a relatively modest pressure was determined to be necessary to ensure quite rapid infiltration of the fiber network. Improvement in ultimate tensile strength and elastic modulus at 100 degrees, 200 degrees, 250 degrees and 300 degrees C over the base alloy (Al-9%Si-3%Cu) upon alumina fiber incorporation was observed. Similar mechanical property improvements resulting from ceramic fiber reinforcement in aluminum alloys have been reported (6, 7).

The purpose of this work is to evaluate the mechanical properties of Standard Oil's low cost aluminosilicate fibers (Fiberfrax®) in aluminum alloys and to determine whether or not the fiber is an adequate reinforcement for aluminum alloys used in automotive engine applications.

Reported in this paper are the characteristics of Standard Oil's Fiberfrax® fiber preforms and the tensile, fatigue and wear properties of the fiber reinforced aluminum alloys. The results of microstructural examination and fracture analysis on the tested specimens are also included.

EXPERIMENTAL

STARTING MATERIAL — The fiber used was Standard Oil reinforcement grade (RG) Fiberfrax® fiber, and the metal used was AA339.0 aluminum alloy, which has a nominal composition of 12% Si, 2.3% Cu, <1.2% Fe, 1.0% Mg, 1.0% Ni and <1.0% Zn.

PROCESSING — The fiber was first made into a preform which is a pre-shaped fiber assemblage with the fibers having appropriate lengths, diameters and orientations. The preform is prepared by mixing the ceramic fiber, inorganic binder and organic binder in a slurry dispersion. The liquid in the slurry is partially removed to form a wet cake with a pre-determined shape. The wet cake is then dried at a temperature above 100 degrees C and subsequently heated at an appropriate temperature to remove the organic binder.

Finally, the preform is infiltrated with aluminum alloy during pressure, or squeeze, casting to form a fiber reinforced aluminum alloy composite. A T5 heat treatment was carried out on the composite prior to mechanical property evaluation.

CHARACTERIZATION METHODS — Ultimate tensile strength and 0.2% offset yield strength were measured, fatigue tests were carried out, microstructural examination and fractographic analysis were performed on the Fiberfrax® fiber reinforced AA339.0 aluminum alloy composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CERAMIC FIBER — The ceramic fibers used as a reinforcement for aluminum alloy in this study are of aluminosilicate compositions and are manufactured by melting/blowing and melting/spinning methods. The discontinuous fibers generally have a composition of about 48 wt. % alumina and 52 wt. % silica. These fibers have an average diameter of 2.0 to 3.0 micrometers depending on the exact chemistry of the material and whether they are spun or blown. The aspect ratio, the ratio of length to diameter of the fiber, ranges from 200 to over

1000. The unfiberized particulate, normally representing 40 to 50% by weight of the fiber, is removed prior to incorporating the fiber into the aluminum alloy. The particulates are removed, because they do not provide reinforcement and do act as stress risers. Typical physical properties of the fibers are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Typical Physical Properties of Standard Oil Fiberfrax® Fibers

Phase	Amorphous
Chemistry	48 wt.% Al ₂ O ₃ , 52 wt.% SiO ₂
Avg. Fiber Diameter	2 to 3 μm
Density	2.73 g/cc
Tensile Strength	1.60 GPa (230 ksi)
Elastic Modulus	104 GPa (15 msi)
Melting Point	1793°C

The fiber tensile strength, 1.6 GPa (230 ksi) at room temperature is about seven times greater than that of cast AA339.0 aluminum alloy and is more than adequate to reinforce the aluminum alloy. The fiber is particularly useful as a reinforcement at elevated temperature because its tensile strength and elastic modulus remain virtually unchanged, even at the melting point of the aluminum alloy. In contrast, the tensile strength and modulus of the aluminum alloy are significantly reduced at elevated temperatures.

FIBER PREFORMS — Casting is a very common method for fabricating automotive engine parts, such as pistons and connecting rods. Therefore, it is desirable to directly incorporate the fiber reinforcement into the casting process. One of the approaches is to prepare a pre-shaped fiber assemblage, or preform. This preform has enough porosity to allow molten metal to infiltrate it during the casting process. The main advantages of preform usage are that 1) The preform provides selective reinforcement capability, and 2) The part manufacturers do not have to be involved with fiber processing. For example, one can selectively reinforce the piston crown without reinforcing the piston skirt.

In order for the fiber reinforced aluminum alloy to achieve good mechanical properties, the preforms must contain fibers which have characteristics meeting the requirements basic to the composite theory for discontinuous fiber reinforcements (8, 9). In addition, the preform should have adequate compressive strength to sustain applied infiltration pressure and to enable final machining to tight tolerances. The ability to accurately match the preform shapes with the shape of final finished parts is also very important, since net-shape castings require a minimum of finishing.

It has been observed that the fibers in Fiberfrax® fiber preforms are fairly evenly distributed, and most of the fibers are oriented in pre-determined orientations. Taking a round disk preform as an example, the fibers are oriented randomly on the disk plane. In the ring preform the fibers can be oriented in the same manner as in the disk or circumferentially as shown in Figure 2. The compressive strength of the Fiberfrax® fiber preforms was satisfactory because the preforms could be machined to tight tolerances and could sustain

Figure 2 — Preform Fiber Orientations

infiltration pressure without cracking. Preforms with fiber volume fraction of .05 to .30 were prepared. Typical fiber preforms and their squeeze cast counterparts are shown in Figure 1.

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE FABRICATION — Engine parts are generally produced by investment and permanent mold casting methods. However, in the presence of the fiber, the traditional gravity casting methods cannot be utilized satisfactorily. This is because the molten aluminum, which has much higher surface energy than the fiber, does not wet the fiber (10). The poor fiber wetting results in a weak composite.

The squeeze casting process (11, 12) now in commercial use involves casting parts under high pressure. The high pressures used in this method not only improve the penetration and spreading of the molten aluminum into the preform and onto the fibers respectively, but also squeeze out voids and porosity, thereby improving the microstructure of the aluminum.

To produce a fiber reinforced part, generally a moderate pressure of greater than 5MPa is first applied to force the molten aluminum through the preform. Then, a much higher pressure of greater than 200MPa is applied during final solidification (13). The preform must be fully infiltrated before applying high pressure, or damage to the preform will occur. Typical Fiberfrax® fiber reinforced pistons are shown in Figure 1.

WEAR CHARACTERISTICS — Five volume percent of Fiberfrax® fiber and 5 vol. % of Fibermax™ fiber (a much higher cost fiber than Fiberfrax® fiber with a polycrystalline mullite composition) were squeeze cast into AA332.0 aluminum alloy. Samples from the above two fiber reinforced composites, along with the base alloy, were given a T5 heat treatment and tested for wear using an LFW-1 test machine (1). The sample was rubbed against a nodular cast iron ring, lubricated with 15W-40 engine oil. The results in Figure 3 indicate that the wear resistance of the fiber reinforced parts is significantly superior to the base alloy. The wear depth of the base alloy is 11 and 18 times deeper than the Fiberfrax® fiber and Fibermax™ fiber reinforced composites respectively. There is no practical advantage to using more expensive Fibermax™ fiber over Fiberfrax® fiber. The orientation of the fiber had little influence on the wear characteristics of the composites. These results are comparable to those for 5 vol. % alumina fiber reinforced AA332.0 aluminum alloy reported by Toaz (3).

Figure 3 — Wear of AA332.0 Aluminum Alloy Reinforced with 5 vol. % Ceramic Fiber

TENSILE PROPERTIES — The focus of our current development work is primarily on piston reinforcement. Therefore, the tensile property evaluations were confined to samples within the 15 to 25 volume percent fiber loading regime known to provide significant strengthening. Preforms with fiber volume fraction of .18 and .23 were incorporated into AA339.0 aluminum alloy by means of squeeze casting followed by a T5 heat treatment. Tensile specimens with threaded ends were prepared and tested according to ASTM-E8, tension testing of metallic materials.

The tensile specimens were tested at 22 degrees C and at 260 degrees C after heat aging at 260 degrees C for 100 hours in air. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and 0.2% offset yield strength (YS) are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2
Tensile Properties of Fiberfrax® Fiber Reinforced AA339.0 Aluminum Alloy

% Fiber Volume	UTS MPa (ksi)		YS MPa (ksi)	
	22° C	260° C	22° C	260° C
0	221 (32.0)	104 (15.0)	173 (25.0)	62 (9.0)
18	250 (36.2)	184 (26.7)	228 (33.0)	120 (17.4)
23	223 (32.3)	174 (25.2)	—	124 (18.0)

It is clearly indicated in Table 2 that the UTS and YS are increased upon incorporation of Fiberfrax® fiber into the aluminum alloy. The improvement in UTS and YS at 22 degrees C over the base alloy is relatively low. For example, the increase in UTS at 22 degrees C for 18 vol. % and 23 vol. % fiber reinforced composites over the base alloy is 13% and 1%, respectively. The 22 degrees C YS increase is 32% over the base alloy for 18 vol. % fiber composite. No YS was determined for the 23 vol. % samples because of the composite's low failure strain.

In contrast, the tensile property improvement is much better at 260 degrees C. For example, the increase over the base alloy in UTS is better than 65%, and in YS is over 90% for both 18 vol. % and 23 vol. % fiber composite samples at 260 degrees C. The better reinforcement performance of the fiber at elevated temperatures is understandable because both UTS and YS of the base alloy are much lower at elevated temperatures, but the UTS of the fiber remains virtually unchanged.

The above results also indicate that there is no significant advantage to using 23 vol. % instead of 18 vol. % fiber because 18 vol. % fiber gives higher UTS and YS at 22 degrees C, and comparable UTS and YS at 260 degrees C. It was also found that at 260 degrees C there is no significant difference in UTS and YS between 100 hours and 1000 hours heat aged samples. It should be pointed out that the tensile properties shown here are comparable to those of 15 vol. % alumina fiber reinforced AA332.0 aluminum alloy reported by Toaz (3), and 20 vol. % alumina fiber reinforced AA339.0 aluminum alloy reported by Spengler and Young (4).

FATIGUE PROPERTIES — Materials used in automotive pistons require high fatigue strength at piston operating temperatures. To establish the fatigue strength of squeeze cast, Fiberfrax® fiber reinforced Aluminum Alloy AA339.0, fatigue tests were performed at 288° C, the upper-intermediate temperature to which heavy duty diesel engine pistons are exposed. Specimens with two levels of Fiberfrax® fiber reinforcement, 15 vol. % and 20 vol. %, and the base alloy itself were subjected to a constant amplitude tension load with an A value of 0.9 and an R value of 0.05 at 29 Hz. The fatigue test results are presented in tabular form in Table 3 and graphical form in Figure 4.

The results of these preliminary tests show that Fiberfrax® fiber reinforcement provides a clear improvement in fatigue properties. The results also indicate that the fatigue properties of the 15 and 20 vol. % fiber reinforced materials are comparable to each other. However, the limited data do suggest a trend toward superior performance of lower fiber content material at lower applied cyclical stresses and superior performance of higher fiber content material at higher applied cyclical stresses. This trend was also exhibited by Spengler and Young (4) for squeeze cast 10 and 20 vol. % aluminum fiber reinforced AA339.0.

TABLE 3
 Fatigue Properties of 15 vol. % and 20 vol. % Fiberfrax®
 Fiber Reinforced AA339.0 Aluminum Alloy at 288° C

Max. Stress MPa (ksi)	Cycles to Failure		
	15 vol. % Fiber Reinforced	20 vol. % Fiber Reinforced	Base Alloy
117 (17)	2.543×10^5	3.490×10^5	—
104 (15)	1.231×10^6	2.750×10^6	—
97 (14)	2.005×10^6	1.033×10^6	7.740×10^5
90 (13)	5.247×10^6	4.595×10^6	—
83 (12)	$*10.082 \times 10^6$	9.653×10^6	3.846×10^6

*Run-out: sample did not fail

Figure 4 — Fatigue at 288° C of AA339.0 Aluminum Alloy Reinforced with 15 vol. % and 20 vol. % Fiberfrax® Fiber

MICROSTRUCTURE AND FRACTOGRAPHY — Fractured tensile specimens of 23 vol. % Fiberfrax® fiber reinforced aluminum alloy AA339.0 composite were sectioned and prepared for metallographic examination. A photomicrograph of the composite structure near the fracture surface is shown in Figure 5.

This photomicrograph shows that the application of high pressure during the squeeze casting process has produced intimate contact between the matrix and the fibers. No shrinkage porosity or interfacial voids are present in the microstructure. Cracking of the fibers and the eutectic silicon phase (medium-gray constituent) is evident in a narrow region adjacent to the fracture surface where the strain is the highest because of localized necking of the tensile specimen. This cracking indicates that the fiber-matrix bond is sufficiently strong to allow effective load transfer to the fibers. Cracks in the fibers become less frequent as the distance from the fracture surface increases because the local strain level decreases.

Figure 5 — Photomicrograph of 23 vol. % Fiberfrax® Fiber Reinforced AA339.0 Aluminum Alloy at 22° C. (Arrows identify the location of cracks in the fibers and silicon phase.)

The fracture surfaces of the tensile bars were macroscopically brittle in appearance. A scanning electron microscope examination revealed that the room temperature specimens exhibited very limited microplasticity in the matrix, and that most of the fibers were broken flush with the fracture surface, as shown in Figure 6a. The specimens tested at 260 degrees C exhibited more matrix microplasticity and a limited amount of fiber-matrix debonding and fiber pull-out, as shown in Figures 6b and 6c. The increase in fiber-matrix debonding at elevated temperature results from a decrease in the interfacial strength of the composite. The interfacial strength is reduced by the decrease in matrix shear strength with increasing temperature, and a weakening of the mechanical bond between the fiber and matrix developed during cooling from the casting temperature. This mechanical bond results from the large coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber and matrix materials.

Figure 6a

Figure 6b

Figure 6c

Figures 6a, 6b and 6c — Scanning Electron Micrographs of 23 vol. % Fiberfrax® Fiber Reinforced AA339.0 Aluminum Alloy Fracture Surfaces (a) at 22° C, (b) at 260° C, and (c) at 260° C.

The fracture surfaces of two 20 vol. % fiber reinforced fatigue specimens, which were tested under maximum stresses of 97 and 104 MPa, were examined by light and scanning electron microscopy. Both fracture surfaces were similar in appearance. No region of classical fatigue crack growth was readily apparent on either surface. The fracture surfaces exhibited a region of rapid crack propagation, with a chevron pattern pointing to a failure initiation site at or near the outside surface of the specimen, as shown in Figure 7a. At high magnifications, this region reveals evidence of fiber pull-out and metal matrix ductility, as shown in Figure 7b.

Figure 7a

Figure 7b

Figures 7a and 7b — Scanning Electron Micrograph of the 20 vol. % Fiberfrax® Fiber Reinforced Fatigue Specimen Fracture Surface at 288° C (a) 18X, and (b) 2000X.

CONCLUSIONS

It was demonstrated that the tensile and fatigue properties of an aluminum alloy can be significantly improved by incorporating low cost aluminosilicate Fiberfrax® fiber. The wear resistance of an aluminum alloy can also be greatly improved by incorporating as low as 5 volume percent of the same Fiberfrax® fiber.

Microstructural and fractographic examination of the squeeze cast, discontinuous aluminosilicate fiber reinforced AA339.0 aluminum alloy composites indicated the presence of intimate fiber/matrix contact, the absence of matrix shrinkage porosity, or interfacial voids, and a brittle macroscopic fracture appearance with limited microplasticity. A limited amount of fiber/matrix debonding and fiber pull-out was observed in 260 degree C samples.

Because of the enhanced metal properties obtained by using low cost aluminosilicate fiber, it is anticipated that the commercialization of metal matrix composites for automotive applications will be encouraged.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to express their thanks to R. Austen for preparing the preforms, and R. Rosenkrantz for providing helpful suggestions.

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